

Thiazolyazo derivatives of some unsaturated β -diketones and their metal complexes

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Abstract : Thiazolyazo derivatives of three β -diketones in which the diketo function attached directly to olefinic linkage(s) [dicinnamoylmethane, acetylcinnamoylmethane and benzoylcinnamoylmethane] have been synthesized and characterized. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data indicate that the compounds exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded azo-enol tautomeric form. Monobasic tridentate coordination of the compounds in their [ML₂] complexes [M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}] has been established on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

Keywords : Substituted diketones, curcuminoids, metal complexes.

In continuation of our studies on arylazo¹ and heteroarylazo² derivatives of 1,3-diketones and their metal complexes, we here report the synthesis and characterization of thiazolyazo derivatives of three diketones in which the diketo function is directly attached to olefinic linkage(s). Such unsaturated 1,3-diketones have gained considerable importance³ in recent years mainly because of the fact that these structural types constitute the major biologically active compounds present in several traditional Indian medicinal plants. The best-known example is the curcuminoids, the active chemical constituent of the herbaceous Indian medicinal plant turmeric (*Curcuma longa*, Linn., *Zingiberacea* family). Curcuminoids, their synthetic analogues and their metal complexes are known to exhibit anticancer, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities⁴. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of thiazolyazo derivatives of three synthetic analogues of the natural curcuminoids namely 1,7-diphenyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione (dicinnamoylmethane); 6-phenyl-5-hexene-2,4-dione (acetylcinnamoylmethane) and 1,5-diphenyl-4-pentene-1,3-dione (benzoylcinnamoylmethane) and their metal complexes.

Results and discussion

The observed elemental analytical data of the thiazolyazo derivatives (Table 1) indicate that diazo-coupling reaction has occurred in the 1 : 1 ratio. All the compounds are crystalline in nature and soluble in common organic solvents and formed stable complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The analytical

data (Table 2) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF (specific conductance <10 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) suggest [ML₂] stoichiometry of the complexes. The Cu^{II} complexes show magnetic moment in the range 1.75–1.80 B.M. and Ni^{II} complexes around 2.85 B.M. The observed IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data are in conformity with structure **1** of thiazolyazo derivatives and structure **2** of the complexes.

Compd.	R	R ₁
Htad	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅
Htah	-CH ₃	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅
Htap	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₅

Infrared spectra : The IR spectrum of Htad in the region 1600–1800 cm⁻¹ shows two strong peaks at 1702 and 1640 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively to the stretching of free and enolised cinnamoyl carbonyl groups^{5,6} of structure **1**. The IR spectrum of Htah also displayed strong bands at 1705 cm⁻¹ due to a free cinnamoyl carbonyl and at 1624 cm⁻¹ due to the enolised acetyl carbonyl^{5,6}. Two bands appeared at 1652 and 1628 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of Htap can be assigned respectively to the free benzoyl carbonyl^{5,6} and enolised cinnamoyl carbonyl of structure **1**.

Table 1. Analytical and ¹H NMR spectral data of Htad, Htah and Htap

Compound/ empirical formula	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)			¹ H NMR (δ ppm)			
			Found (Calcd)			OH	Alkenyl	Aryl/ thiazolyl	Alkyl
			C	H	N				
Htad C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ SO ₂	160	75	68.28 (68.22)	4.36 (4.40)	10.82 (10.85)	13.18	8.13 (2H) 7.94 (2H)	6.80–7.80	–
Htah C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₂	140	72	60.16 (60.20)	4.34 (4.35)	13.98 (14.05)	13.26	7.92 (1H) 7.62 (1H)	6.80–7.50	2.56 (3H)
Htap C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ SO ₂	171	70	63.70 (63.83)	7.92 (7.98)	11.11 (11.17)	12.92	7.96 (1H) 7.67 (1H)	6.50–7.58	–

In the spectra of all the three compounds two medium intensity bands are observed at ~1280 and 1450 cm⁻¹ assignable to C–O–H in plane bending and νN=N respectively^{7,8}. The thiazole ring νC=N is observed in the range 1600–1610 cm⁻¹. Spectra of the compounds showed a broad band ranging from 2350 to 3500 cm⁻¹ due to strong O–H...N hydrogen bonding. Thus the IR spectra strongly support the existence of the compounds in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded azo-enol tautomeric form.

In the IR spectra of all the complexes the broad free ligand band in the region 2350–3500 cm⁻¹ disappeared indicating the replacement of the enol proton by metal ion during complexation². Several medium intensity bands are present in the region of the spectra due to various νC–H vibrations. The absence of the free ligand band at ~1280 cm⁻¹ due to C–O–H bending also support the replacement of the enol proton by metal ion. The free cinnamoyl band of Htad and Htah is only marginally shifted indicating that this carbonyl is not involved in coordination. However, the band due to the hydrogen bonded carbonyl group disappeared and instead a new band appeared at ~1550 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the complexes supporting the involvement of the enolised carbonyl in bonding with the metal ion. In the spectra of complexes of Htap the benzoyl carbonyl band suffered only slight shift while the cinnamoyl carbonyl disappeared and a new band observed at ~1560 cm⁻¹ assignable to metal bonded carbonyl function. In the spectra of all the complexes, the band at ~1450 cm⁻¹ due to νN=N and the band due to thiazole νC=N (1600–1610 cm⁻¹) of the free ligand shifted appreciably to low wave number (~20–30 cm⁻¹) indicating the involvement of these groups in bonding with the metal ion as in structure 2. The presence of new medium intensity bands at ~425 and ~530 cm⁻¹ assignable to νM–O and νM–N in the spectra of all the complexes⁹ also support structure 2. Since the spectra of all the complexes are of similar nature only important bands that appeared in the spectra of the thiazolylazo derivatives and their Cu^{II} complexes are given in Table 3.

¹H NMR spectra: The ¹H NMR spectra of the thiazolylazo derivatives of unsaturated 1,3-diketones are characterized by

the presence of a low field one proton signal at ~δ 13 ppm which is considerably lower than that reported for arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones that exist in the hydrazone form¹. Since azo-enol protons show signal in the range δ 10–14 ppm, the signal at ~δ 13 ppm can be assigned to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol proton^{1,2,10}. The alkenyl protons are observed in the range δ 7.6–8.2 ppm and aryl protons in δ 6.5–7.5 ppm (Table 1). In the ¹H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Zn^{II} complexes, the low field signal due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded OH proton disappeared indicating its replacement by metal cation during complexation. The integrated intensities of various signals agree well with the [ML₂] stoichiometry of the complexes.

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of the metal complexes of Htad, Htah and Htap

Complex/ empirical formula	Yield (%)	M p (°C)	Elemental analysis (%)			
			Found (Calcd)			
			C	H	N	M
[Cu(tad) ₂] C ₄₄ H ₃₂ CuN ₆ S ₂ O ₄	60	256	63.10 (63.19)	3.78 (3.83)	9.98 (10.05)	7.50 (7.60)
[Cu(tah) ₂] C ₃₀ H ₂₄ CuN ₆ S ₂ O ₄	65	286	54.40 (54.58)	3.60 (3.64)	12.65 (12.74)	9.54 (9.63)
[Cu(tap) ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ CuN ₆ S ₂ O ₄	70	278	61.23 (61.26)	3.54 (3.57)	10.64 (10.72)	8.02 (8.11)
[Ni(tad) ₂] C ₄₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ NiS ₂ O ₄	65	258	63.44 (63.56)	3.84 (3.85)	10.16 (10.11)	6.99 (7.07)
[Ni(tah) ₂] C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ NiS ₂ O ₄	65	242	54.86 (54.99)	3.63 (3.67)	12.73 (12.83)	8.85 (8.97)
[Ni(tap) ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ NiS ₂ O ₄	75	264	61.55 (61.64)	3.55 (3.60)	10.68 (10.79)	7.55 (7.54)
[Zn(tad) ₂] C ₄₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ S ₂ O ₄ Zn	68	206	62.98 (63.05)	3.78 (3.82)	10.10 (10.03)	7.85 (7.81)
[Zn(tah) ₂] C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂ O ₄ Zn	70	198	54.36 (54.43)	3.53 (3.63)	12.63 (12.70)	9.75 (9.89)
[Zn(tap) ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ S ₂ O ₄ Zn	66	210	61.18 (61.12)	3.53 (3.57)	10.63 (10.70)	8.45 (8.32)

Table 3. Characteristic IR stretching bands (cm^{-1}) and mass spectral data of Htad, Htah, Htap and their Cu^{II} complexes

Compd.	IR bands (cm^{-1})							Mass spectral data (m/z)
	Free (C=O)	Chelated (C=O)	(C=N)	(C=C) phenyl/ alkenyl	(N=N)	(M-N)	(M-O)	
Htad	1702	1640	1605	1595, 1590, 1588, 1580	1455	–	–	387, 359, 303, 289, 275, 256, 131, 125, 103, 84, 77
Htah	1705	1624	1608	1598, 1595, 1588, 1582	1445	–	–	299, 271, 256, 215, 201, 187, 168, 131, 125, 84, 77
Htap	1652	1628	1605	1599, 1596, 1590, 1586	1450	–	–	376, 348, 292, 278, 271, 264, 245, 140, 131, 125, 105, 84, 77
$[\text{Cu}(\text{tad})_2]$	1698	1542	1582	1598, 1594, 1590, 1587	1430	518 510	422	837, 835, 706, 704, 795, 793, 575, 573, 734, 732, 631, 629, 387, 359, 303, 256, 131, 125, 103, 84, 77
$[\text{Cu}(\text{tah})_2]$	1698	1555	1578	1602, 1598, 1590, 1586	1420	520 510	428	661, 659, 530, 528, 618, 616, 399, 397, 575, 573, 558, 556, 455, 453, 299, 271, 256, 187, 168, 125, 131, 77
$[\text{Cu}(\text{tap})_2]$	1650	1562	1580	1598, 1593, 1589, 1586	1425	528 522	425	815, 813, 773, 771, 712, 710, 708, 684, 682, 609, 553, 551, 376, 348, 278, 271, 140, 131, 125, 84, 77

Mass spectra : The formulation of the compounds as in structure 1 is clearly supported from the presence of intense molecular ion peak in the mass spectra. Presence of peaks due to the elimination of N_2 from molecular ion, characteristic of tautomers^{11,12} in the spectra support the azo structure. Fragments due to the elimination of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCO}$, CH_3CO , thiazole group, etc. are typical of the spectra (Table 3). The origin of the peak at m/z 125 can be explained by the formation of the ion radical $[\text{T-N}_2\text{CH}]^+$ (T = thiazole ring) through the elimination of RCO and R_1CO from P^+ . Had the compounds existed in the hydrazone form, the most facile reaction involve the cleavage of N–N bond¹² and the ion of m/z 125 would not have originated. Thus all available evidences support the existence of the compounds in the azo-enol form rather than the keto-hydrazone form. The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks corresponding to $[\text{CuL}_2]$ stoichiometry. Peaks correspond to $[\text{P-RCO}]^+$, $[\text{P-R}_1\text{CO}]^+$, $[\text{RCO}]^+$, $[\text{R}_1\text{CO}]^+$, $[\text{CuL}]^+$, L^+ and fragments of L^+ are also present in the spectra. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu isotopes (Table 3).

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by micro analyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The IR spectra (KBr discs) were recorded on a 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at 28 ± 1 °C using solution of about 10^{-3} M concentration.

Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of thiazolylazo derivative of unsaturated 1,3-diketones, Htad, Htah and Htap : The unsaturated 1,3-diketones, 1.7-diphenyl-1.6-heptadiene-3,5-dione; 6-phenyl-5-hexene-2,4-dione and 1.5-diphenyl-4-pentene-1,3-dione were synthesized as reported^{5,13}. An aqueous solution of thiazole-2-diazonium ion was prepared by standard method¹⁴. After destroying the excess nitrous acid with urea, the solution was added drop by drop with stirring to an ice cold (< 5 °C) solution of the unsaturated 1,3-diketone (0.01 mol, 20 mL ethanol). Sodium acetate was added to adjust the pH around 6. Stirring was continued for about half an hour and the precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized twice from hot methanol to get chromatographically (TLC) pure compound.

Synthesis of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes : A concentrated aqueous solution of metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol, 15 mL) was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol, 20 mL). The mixture was refluxed on a hot water bath for ~3 h and poured into crushed ice with constant stirring. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with water, recrystallised from hot methanol and dried in vacuum.

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